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INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING THE FRENCH LANGUAGE IN TEACHING INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN UKRAINE

Abstract.

The article examines one of the problems of teaching the French language - the need to introduce innovative technologies and methods of linguistic didactics into the process of learning French by students of language specialties. Special attention is paid to the use of communicative learning methods and the language classroom as methods of active development of students' communicative and linguistic-cultural competence.

Keywords: methodology; innovative technologies; language office; French; gaming technologies; project methodology.

Statement of the problem. Linguistic culture has always been and remains an integral component of human culture. Taking into account the integration of Ukraine into Europe and its standards, the problem of language learning as one of the means of intercultural interaction in the social and professional sphere is relevant for today. However, at this stage there is an acute problem of improving the quality of learning the French language - the lack of a sufficient number of educational and methodological literature and textbooks for all levels of education, which would meet modern requirements, incorporating the material necessary for the formation of communicative speech competences and the expansion of cultural and sociocultural students' knowledge of the French language, cultural characteristics of native speakers, their habits, traditions, norms of behavior and etiquette.

The purpose of the article. Consider methods of increasing the effectiveness of French language learning in pedagogical institutions of higher education.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The issue of increasing the effectiveness of learning foreign languages is devoted to the research of such scientists as H.M. Bros, M.V. Claren, L.V. Pirozhenko, O.I. Pomitun and others. However, the vast majority of scientific works are related to the study of Romance and Germanic languages, the relevance of which is determined by their active use in the political and economic spheres of international relations. Today, teachers of the French language face the important task of optimizing the learning process, increasing the effectiveness of language learning by students. All extracurricular activities, non-traditional techniques, new methods of learning, all that the teacher brings to a regular lesson in a complex discipline, are used precisely for the purpose of creating internal motivation of students to study this subject.

Presentation of the main research material. The individuality of languages and cultures should be noted in the language learning process. Knowing another language acquires a special value if it is related to the un-

derstanding of the culture, knowledge about the relations, imaginations and stereotypes of the representatives of the language being studied.

Presentation of the main research material. To date, there is no single classification of teaching methods that covers the wide and diverse range of traditional and non-traditional methods of teaching French. It is impossible to stop at the use of certain methods separately. Effective teaching of the French language in pedagogical institutions of higher education can be achieved by a harmonious combination of traditional and non-traditional teaching methods. Innovative technologies include such approaches to language teaching as interactive teaching methods and the use of technical teaching aids. The term "interactive" is borrowed into the Ukrainian language from the English language and has the meaning "interactive". Interactive learning is, first of all, dialogic learning, in the process of which the teacher and student interact [1; p. 131].

The importance of interactive methods lies in the fact that students are not afraid to express their opinions, they can both agree and disagree with the expressed ideas of others. Such methods are divided into four methods of educational activity: paired (student-teacher, student-student), frontal (the teacher teaches a group or subgroup), group, individual [2]. Practice shows that interactive learning tools contribute to increasing motivation, consolidation of knowledge, development of creativity and communication skills of students. The use of interactive methods corresponds to the modern concept of education, which is based on the principle of active student activity. There are the following types of interactive approaches: 1. Project methodology. With the help of the project methodology, it is possible to achieve several goals at once - to activate and spread the vocabulary, to consolidate the studied lexical and grammatical material [3].

The project method can be implemented within the curriculum on almost any topic. Various tools can be used for the project task - multimedia presentations, drawings, collages, diagrams, tables, graphs and charts. The project is carried out according to a certain scheme: preparation (choice of the topic, formulation of the

problem and goal); organization of the project (drawing up an action plan, outlining tasks for each student); implementation of the project (search for necessary information, choice of method of implementation and presentation of the project); project presentation; summing up. The presentation of the project is carried out in the audience using multimedia tools 2. Game technologies. The term "game pedagogical technologies" includes a large group of methods and techniques for organizing the pedagogical process. The works of E. Passov, M. Skatkin, D. Elkonin [4] are devoted to the use of game methods in foreign language learning.

With the help of game technologies, students acquire problem-solving skills, practice using grammatical constructions, and practice linguistic and cultural realities. Game technologies, in turn, can be divided into the following types: Debate is considered an effective means of language teaching due to the fact that it provides an opportunity to develop all four language skills - listening, reading, speaking and writing. During debates on a given topic, students improve their listening and speaking skills, as well as their writing skills, as participants take notes on their opponents' responses in order to offer their own counterarguments. In particular, the implementation of this type of game technology requires serious preparation on the part of the participants, because students need to analyze the literature in accordance with the specified topic, draw up a synopsis plan and select the theses and provisions that are adequate for the communicative situation. Role-playing is an active method of learning, a means of developing the student's communicative abilities. Role playing helps to overcome language barriers of students, significantly increases the scope of their speaking practice [5].

In role-playing games, the social role relations of the participants are necessarily formed. Students are required not only to solve the task, but also to play their social role correctly [6]. When teaching the French language, it is possible to use such well-known forms of interactive methods as "Brainstorming", "Associative bush", "Mosaic", "Complete the phrase", "Taboo" and others. This type of game facilitates learning a certain grammatical form. The use of technical teaching aids is an integral part of innovative language teaching methods. Language training of foreign language specialists requires daily training, including simulation of the language environment in classrooms. Listening to audio recordings, watching cartoons and movies helps students feel the linguistic atmosphere of the country whose language they are studying. In this case, language classrooms, multimedia laboratories and interactive classes provide students with significant help and improvement of their foreign language skills.

The vast majority of interactive classes are designed for both group work in classes and independent work of students. Thus, the use of information technologies in the process of learning a foreign language helps to increase oral practice for each student, ensure high motivation for learning, and make the learning process more interesting. Modern language classrooms act as new means of teaching a foreign language. They are used to conduct various types of classes as a means of

presenting educational information, monitoring the assimilation of knowledge, developing certain skills in students, and automating the educational process. The language classroom is a classroom equipped with language systems for modern education. The speech system is a complex of sound engineering and projection equipment for reproduction and recording of audiovisual effects. Each of the workplaces is provided with a telephone-microphone headset with microphones of reduced sensitivity and directional activity. This design allows all students to talk out loud without disturbing each other.

Software is installed on the computers of the language classrooms, which has a large set of functions, which allows the teacher to effectively and interestingly conduct foreign language training: - the function of creating a class model (each teacher can create a class/s and register students in them); - screen broadcast (the teacher can broadcast what is happening on his screen to one or more students in full-screen or windowed mode. In full-screen mode, the broadcast occupies the entire screen, and the student cannot use other programs that are allowed in windowed mode); - demonstration of a student (the teacher can select a student to demonstrate his actions on the screens of other students; he can also communicate with the selected student, and other students can hear it); - remote control (in addition to screen broadcasting, the teacher can choose any programs to run on students' screens, allow or prohibit the use of certain programs, observe students' actions, stop computers) - drawing (the teacher can draw, write, insert autoshapes or making pencil marks on the student's screen, these actions are also available for demonstration to the whole class); - playback of video and audio materials (the teacher can play video and audio files over the network, add other audio and video files to the playlist, cut the video, add subtitles, make bookmarks for the necessary passages); - the webcam function (the teacher can broadcast video and sounds from the webcam on the students' screens, the function is useful for various phonetic exercises); - interactive whiteboard (allows the teacher and students to work with one interactive whiteboard at the same time, you can upload text files and pictures to the whiteboard; the function is useful for performing exercises in a group, solving crosswords, conducting quizzes, information on the whiteboard can be saved for later use); - tape recorder and tutor (intended for listening to educational material with subtitles in various learning modes; the teacher can define such tasks for the student to work with the tape recorder as listening to a sound file, recording his voice on a tape recorder, listening to his recording); - conversation in groups (the teacher can organize live oral and written learning in groups, the selected function will be performed simultaneously for all groups created in the class, the teacher and students of the selected group can hear each other, work on a written task in the form of text correspondence between the teacher and students, the teacher can connect to any group for conversation and sending text tasks); - conversation by topic (the teacher can create several educational topics with texts and pictures; the names of the topics will be visible and students can choose the topic

themselves and connect to the task); – exam (allows the teacher to create and edit exam forms; the teacher can create several thematic sections with questions, it is possible to create different types of questions: with multiple-choice answers, “correct/incorrect” questions, general questions, fill-in-the-blank questions, it is possible to determine the number of points for each question and limit the time for taking the exam, the program calculates points for all answers, except general questions, shows statistics); – survey (the function allows the teacher to ask questions and immediately get the answers of students, this function can be used to conduct quizzes, the teacher can mark the correct ones reward answers); – functions for the student (all functions and programs are controlled by the teacher, but the student has the opportunity to perform some independent actions during the lesson: send a text message to the teacher, “raise your hand” to attract the teacher's attention, send/receive files, work with the “tutor” function) [7].

An extremely interesting invention is the use of the functions of the interactive class system in booths for simultaneous translation, which enables students to translate without disturbing each other. And if the students' attention is distracted during translation in the classroom, then being in the booths, they have the opportunity to work individually. At the same time, the teacher can listen to each student (the teacher's monitor has cubicle numbers) [8]. Thus, the presence of a wide range of functions turns the language classroom into a powerful and effective tool for teaching a foreign language, makes it possible to use numerous digital educational resources in the educational process, which qualitatively increases the level of education and allows for a rational distribution of study time. The use of computer-oriented tools in the process of learning foreign languages contributes to increasing interest and general motivation thanks to new forms of work and involvement in the priority direction of scientific and technical progress; activation of training thanks to attractive and rapidly changing forms of information presentation, individualization of training; prompt access to information. The use of computer-oriented learning tools during the study of foreign languages significantly increases the intensity of the educational process, allows you to cover a significant amount of educational material, which is learned more firmly thanks to positive motivation.

Conclusions. The use of innovative technologies makes it possible to increase the efficiency of learning

the French language. The idea of creating educational programs using computers and video recordings, and introducing them into the process of learning a foreign language is extremely promising. Intensification of learning, as one of the important modern trends, dictates the need to modify a foreign language lesson, to turn it into a lesson - an excursion, a lesson - a conference, a lesson - telebridge. Taking into account the individual characteristics of students, the use of various forms of work in the teaching of the French language: independent, paired, group work are important means of improving the quality of education and education of students, allows better consideration of their individual differences, sphere of interests and provides students with the opportunity to achieve the planned result.

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